

**CADRE Solution Architecture
V3.0
27 November 2024**

Project Details

Partners: The Australian National University (ANU), Australian Access Federation (AAF), Melbourne Institute Data Lab (MIDL), Research Graph, Australian Urban Research Infrastructure Network (AURIN), Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW), Australian Institute of Family Studies (AIFS), University of Melbourne, Swinburne University, University of New South Wales (UNSW), Melbourne Institute.

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Revision History

Version	Date	Editor	Summary of Changes
0.1	05/05/2022	Marina McGale	Initial Draft
0.2	09/06/2022	Marina McGale	Edits taking into account feedback and discussion from presenting 0.1 on 05/05/2022
0.3	16/06/2022	Marina McGale	Edits based on feedback from conversation with AURIN on 15/06/2022
1.0	30/11/2022	Marina McGale	Finalising v 1.0 with from v0.3 DRAFT
1.1	20/12/2022	Marina McGale	Updated references to AARNET, replacing with MIDL; Updated diagrams with same
2.0	08/11/2023	Marina McGale	Updated to reflect most recent updates; Updated diagrams.
3.0	27/11/2024	Marina McGale	Updated to reflect most recent technical implementation; Updated diagrams.

Supporting Documents

All CADRE-related documentation is stored in ANU Sharepoint directories for both external CADRE partners and the internal CADRE team.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The details of the CADRE project are documented on the CADRE website:

<https://cadre5safes.org.au>

1.2. Purpose of this Document

The purpose of this document is to detail the baseline architecture for implementation of Phase 1 of the CADRE platform, to be deployed as CADRE V1.0.

1.3. Stakeholders

Stakeholders in the CADRE project are: the Australian Research Data Commons, and the project partners as detailed in the “Partners” subheading of “Project Details” on page 1.

1.4. Scope

1.4.1. In Scope of this Solution Architecture document:

- Phase 1 Platform Architecture

1.4.2. Out of Scope of this Solution Architecture document:

- User Interface design for the CADRE dashboard – the design documents will be separate to this Solution Architecture document.
- Application API specifics
- Federated search of requestable datasets in phase 1 of CADRE
- Negotiation between CADRE and secure environments for storage/compute space (this is anticipated to be coordinated by researchers outside of the CADRE platform in phase 2).
- Coordination of data transfer by CADRE from: storage location to: a secure environment location. The data transfer coordination will be implemented in a future development phase.

2. Baseline Solution Architecture

2.1. Current Services Overview

2.1.1. CILogon/COManage

CILogon2 (s2.1.1) is SAAS that incorporates both CILogon and COManage (CILogon and COManage were separate services in previous versions).

CILogon is a federated Identity Provider through which users will login with their organizational/AAF credentials and, upon successful login, will be redirected back to the CADRE platform dashboard.

CILogon can integrate with other authoritative data sources such as ORCID to retrieve - with the researcher’s consent to attribute release – and assert other relevant data about that researcher that is not provided by AAF. This additional

asserted data will enrich the researcher's CADRE user profile and streamline the data sharing request process by using data from trusted sources as facilitated by CILogon.

In addition to this user profile enrichment, the COManage component of CILogon will manage Collaborative Organizations (COs). This functionality will facilitate creation and management of 1) groups of collaborators within the CADRE platform and 2) projects involving those groups.

CILogon can facilitate international IdPs (edugain for example) thereby facilitating collaboration groups across international organisations. This is a feature that AAF cannot supply as AAF is strictly Australian in context.

CILogon/AAF has deployed a CILogon/COManage test instance in Australia AWS: test.cilogon.aaf.edu.au. When CADRE is deployed to production, the production instance will call an Australian-deployed production CILogon/AAF service.

NOTE: CILogon supports a variety of token formats so there is a verifiable, reusable, time-limited claim that can be reused for future data requests until the token expires.

2.1.2. Research Graph and Augment API

Research Graph (researchgraph.org) provides information about the following research-related objects:

- Researcher
- Publication
- Dataset
- Grant
- Organisation

Upon submission of a Data Sharing Request (DSR), the Approver evaluating the merit of the DSR will be presented with a link out to the web interface of Research Graph with the researcher's ORCID ID. This link can be followed by a request access Approver to get a more in-depth look at all of the researcher's information connected to the above research-related objects. This detailed information will also contribute to the Applicant/Collaborator evaluation as a 'Safe Person'.

Note: this Research Graph/Augment link is dependent on the academic researcher having at least one public ORCID ID that has been updated with their research information. If the researcher does not have at least one public ORCID, it will be impossible to import Research Graph information about them into CADRE platform. Note also that a researcher may initially have a public ORCID, but they can set this ORCID to private, in which case their information will no longer be accessible either through ORCID itself or through Research Graph.

2.1.3. RAiD Service (ARDC)

The ARDC's RAiD service is SAAS that allows registration of a Project as a research activity, and returns a RAiD as a PID attached to that activity.

The RAiD service takes a project name and description as the minimum metadata with which to create a new project.

It is envisioned that creation of a project in CADRE will result in creation of a project in the RAiD service, with a PID attached. CADRE V1.0 has been implemented in anticipation of the production RAiD service becoming fully operational, with features added to facilitate Projects in CADRE being linked to Projects in RAiD.

The RAiD Service has recently been deployed into production. The CADRE development team will conduct a feasibility study to determine how the RAiD service can be integrated into CADRE 2.0.

2.1.4. Melbourne Institute – MIDL (Melbourne Institute Data Lab)

CADRE will provide MIDL (and other external partners) with the following CADRE endpoints:

1. **/api/partner/trainings/add-user-training-details**– to register MIDL users who have completed any MIDL training. These training records will then be accessible in the CADRE trainings/API. See https://admin-stage.cadre.ada.edu.au/swagger-ui/index.html#/partner/post_api_partner_trainings_add_user_training_details for the parameters to be supplied to the endpoint and to test the API.
 - a. Note: a CADRE/REMS user account with role/permissions as a (REMS) Organisation owner is required to use this API endpoint.
 - b. Any other external partners can arrange, upon approval by the CADRE admin team, for an account set up such that they can use this endpoint.
2. **/api/partner/user-details** – to request information that CADRE can supply about a specific user:
 - a. Profile information
 - b. RG summary information (CADRE 2.0)
 - c. Training courses completed
 - d. Number of current Data Sharing Requests (last x months)
 - e. Number of current Data Sharing Agreements (last x months)

Note:

- CADRE/REMS user account with assigned permissions as a (REMS) Organisation owner is required to be able to use this API endpoint.
- Visit https://admin-stage.cadre.ada.edu.au/swagger-ui/index.html#/partner/get_api_partner_user_details to test the API endpoint.

MIDL will likely also be interfacing with ADA's Dataverse instance to create new datasets in a MIDL (sub)dataverse. These new datasets will then be discoverable in the Dataverse instance, and requestable in CADRE.

2.1.5. Dataset Sources – CADRE partners

The datasets to which a user will be able to request access through the CADRE platform will be hosted in external partner data discovery services.

The datasets included in CADRE in phase 1 will be a subset from the Australian Data Archive's production Dataverse (dataverse.ada.edu.au) as proof of concept.

MIDL anticipate creating new datasets in ADA's dataverse.ada.edu.au instance that will then be discoverable in Dataverse, and requestable in CADRE. Data Coop is anticipated to follow this model as well.

AURIN is a fourth partner in the CADRE platform development. It is anticipated that AURIN will request user-related information from the CADRE platform user-details API endpoint, and will use that as input to their own services.

The CADRE Terms and Conditions will require that users of the CADRE platform agree to the following on sign-up:

- the CADRE platform collects data about them from:
 - AAF
 - Research Graph (ORCID and crossref)
 - Moodle (required 5Safes training courses completion status)
 - MIDL training (if relevant), other external training registered in CADRE (if relevant)
 - Any other Training services that write their training results to CADRE
 - Additional information the user provides
- the CADRE platform will share their information with the partners integrated with the CADRE platform
- how this data is stored and how long it is retained

[See Policy Documents](#) for specific details.

2.1.6. External Training System for 5 Safes Training (Moodle)

One aspect of evaluating a researcher as a 'Safe Person' will be if they have successfully completed the 5 Safes Training that will be implemented in the Moodle external training platform (learning.cadre5safes.org.au).

The CADRE platform queries the learning.cadre5safes.org.au Moodle API to determine if a specific user has completed the mandatory 5 Safes training courses and indicate completion status against the user's profile.

3. Baseline Target Solution Architecture

3.1 Solution Architecture for the proposed solution

3.1.1 Phase 1 (V1.0) of the solution architecture will deliver functionality for:

- Researchers to request access (submit 'Data Sharing Requests' (DSRs)) to datasets/resources/assets across several partners without having to key in common data multiple times
 - ADA
 - MIDL
 - Data Coop
- Access Managers from the partner settings to:
 - view DSRs for their corresponding setting datasets
 - Evaluate
 - safe People/Organisations: Academic researchers (future phases will allow government users, NGOs/NFPs)
 - safe Projects
 - safe Data
 - Approve DSRs to generate Data Sharing Agreements (DSAs)

External systems will be integrated: ADA Dataverse, MIDL (training + datasets), Data Co-Op, Moodle, Research Graph/Augment API.

The CADRE platform will be multi-tenanted. Each partner (tenant) will only be able to view DSRs submitted and DSAs created for their organisation's datasets requested in CADRE.

3.1.2 The CADRE platform will include the following areas of functionality:

1. CILogon/COMange – Authentication/Authorisation; Group Management
2. Project Management
3. CADRE web client – the interface that will bring together information from all the other services and external platforms into a decision-making platform to approve or reject a submitted DSR.
4. RESTful API that encapsulates the following functionality:
 - 4.1. Profiles Management– this will aggregate available public information from Research Graph/Augment API, external LMS platforms (Moodle 5 Safes training, MIDL training) and present them to the end user and to the admin user. A users' request and approved history will be presented to the approver in a future release.
 - 4.2. Data Sharing Requests Management – this will manage dataset access requests submitted by users and actioned by approvers/access managers.
 - 4.3. Data Sharing Agreements Management – this will manage the agreements between data applicants and settings to dictate which DSAs are valid at any singular point in time.
 - 4.4. Project Management – this will manage the creation/updating/viewing of projects in the CADRE platform.

- 4.5. Group Management - this will manage Groups (of people) in the CADRE platform in collaboration with COManage.
- 4.6. Documents Management – this will manage deeds and other documents uploaded by data applicants/users. (CADRE 2.0)

3.1.2 Future services to be evaluated for future CADRE development phases:

1. Integrating with the ARDC’s RAiD service when in production, to create Projects and have associated PID returned and used in CADRE.
2. Integrating CADRE to communicate directly with external secure environments to request storage/compute space for the data to which a data applicant is granted access.
3. Coordination of secure transfer of requested data to the secure enclave/data processing.
4. Research Passports (ICSPR project) if deemed a requirement, and if feasible.

Any future proposed features or integrations will be subject to feasibility studies to determine if they are technically possible, or worth the technical effort.

3.1.4 Additional Considerations and Constraints:

Ideally the CADRE platform would be implemented with a micro-services architecture. However, the capacity to employ developers with a micro-services skillset for both implementation and future maintenance is non-existent.

As developers experienced in Microservices design, implementation, deployment and maintenance would be difficult if not impossible to employ in the current academic market, the architecture has been designed as a ‘standard’ 3-tier API-first web application. The front-end consists of a ReactJS dashboard that presents role-based information. The backend is an opensource platform (REMS) with a RESTful API with additional CADRE-specific endpoints. These endpoints are structured and organised into different areas of concern: user profiles, data sharing requests, data sharing agreements, projects, trainings, etc.

3.1.5 Evaluation of pre-existing systems:

Several existing applications and services were evaluated for re-use in the CADRE platform:

- The Notary Service component (<https://github.com/RENCI-NRIG/notary-service>) of the ImPACT platform from the US is well developed but challenging from a usability perspective. It was decided to not re-use the Notary System for CADRE.
- DUOS (<https://duos.broadinstitute.org/home>) was evaluated and while well polished, is tightly integrated with the Terra platform. It was decided not to use this system for CADRE.

The Office of the National Data Commissioner has released the initial DataPlace platform (<https://www.dataplace.gov.au/>) for requesting access to Australian Government datasets. It allows onboarding with 1) Vanguard (the Australian Government SSO system) or 2) AAF for academic researchers or 3) MyGovId. This is another polished platform that provides inspiration for the CADRE platform. A presentation was given to the Sensitive Data Working Group in November 2023.

- The REMS project (source code: <https://github.com/CSCfi/remis>) (demo: <https://rems-demo.rahtiapp.fi/>) is of interest and isn't as complex as ImpACT. REMS does have a few missing features and isn't as polished as DUOS but it is open source and can be extended. It is written in Clojure (API) and ClojureScript (front-end) which is not widely used which implies a steep learning curve for any development work and sustainability of the project after Phase 3 is delivered.
 - REMS is of interest to the BioCommons group and to LdAca – however, these teams use REMS as-is as it fits their requirements without the need for modified nor additional functionality.

Decision:

- It was decided to use the REMS API as the backend, and implement the dashboard frontend (requester and approver) in ReactJS, adding missing CADRE functionality as required.
- There are 3 CADRE/REMS instances deployed to NCI vm's:
 - <https://dev.cadre.ada.edu.au> (admin side to set up resources, etc: <https://admin-dev.cadre.ada.edu.au>)
 - <https://test.cadre.ada.edu.au> (admin side to set up resources, etc: <https://admin-test.cadre.ada.edu.au>)
 - <https://stage.cadre.ada.edu.au> (admin side to set up resources, etc: <https://admin-stage.cadre.ada.edu.au>)

CADRE V1.0 will be deployed into production on <https://cadre.ada.edu.au>.

3.1.5 Other core functionality:

- Monitoring/Logging
 - Logging and monitoring services appropriate for the technologies used to implement the services will be installed and configured to monitor for the appropriate level of issue reporting
- API: Any endpoints required to implement functionality will be determined at design time.
- Databases:
 - The REMS API interfaces with a postgres database
 - The postgres database may need to store extra information related to users and that can't be stored elsewhere in CADRE/REMS or its integrated systems.

Note: CILogon schema is extensible and should be able to store most things if that's the most logical place to store it. CILogon is appropriate to store data about users that is then used to inform decisions about approving access requests – name, email, current org, ORCID, group membership (if user belongs to specific group, can have access).

3.2 Proposed System Architecture Baseline

3.2.1 High Level Platform Architecture

3.2.2 3-Tier web application with API backend

CADRE Technical Architecture Diagram

Phase 1 will deploy the implementation of a multi-tenanted containerised web application

- with a React front end for web-based user interface
- with a REMS API back end that interfaces with a database
- with a middle layer between the API backend and database(s).

Future CADRE phases may involve transitioning away from the REMS backend to a purely CADRE-specific backend with the goal to implement CADRE-specific use cases. This may be implemented via a micro-services architecture, if that is deemed more efficient and there is scope and funding, and developer resources, to do so, or through another n-tier application but with more commonly-used languages.

Proposed Technology stack – Phase 1:

Servers: The dev/test/stage versions of the CADRE platform are currently hosted on NCI vm's. The production version of CADRE (<https://cadre.ada.edu.au>) will also be deployed to an NCI vm. NCI will be able to provide a level of security for this service with its f5 Web Application Firewall (WAF).

Tech stack:

Web-based front end: ReactJS
Back-end API: REMS API (Clojure)
Database: Postgres
Container: Docker

3.2.3 CADRE API Details

3.2.3.1 Proposed Architecture for API endpoint: /profile

API Endpoint: /user-profile

/user-profile <param: user-id>

3.2.3.2 Proposed Architecture for API endpoint: /datasharingrequests

3.2.3.3 Proposed Architecture for API endpoint: /datasharingagreements

3.2.2.4 Proposed Architecture for API endpoint: /projects

3.2.2.5 Proposed Architecture for API endpoint /comments

3.3 Implementation Plan

Please refer to <https://cadre5safes.org.au/about/project-phases/> for the phases of the CADRE project.

4 Interfaces

4.2 User Interfaces

The CADRE platform in production will be accessed through the following user interfaces:

- Role-based Web dashboard for data applicants and approvers:
<https://cadre.ada.edu.au/>
- Web interface for administrators to set up datasets, Organisations, etc:
<https://admin.cadre.ada.edu.au>
- API – access based on endpoint permissions

Design and implementation of the web-based interface will be based on user stories/use cases.

4.3 API Interface Authentication/Authorisation

The REMS API uses API keys for auth/auth. An API key must be generated by a CADRE admin user and transmitted securely to the target user.

5 Information Security

5.1 Datasets/Assets

The unit record data of datasets will not be accessible through the CADRE platform. Only a minimal set of metadata for datasets/assets will be presented to end users as the basis for their search and Data Sharing Requests. Once a Data Sharing Request has been approved, creating a Data Sharing Agreement, the user will be given access to the data in some way determined by the setting owner/custodian of that data.

In future phases, it is anticipated that the CADRE platform will be able to 1) directly negotiate secure storage in secure environments and then 2) coordinate/initiate the transfer of the data from the data storage to the secure environment using a tool such as Globus (as an example). The technical feasibility of this transfer requires that the recipient safe setting allows this transfer from a policy/governance point of view, and that the technical endpoint exists for the recipient safe setting to be able to accept the transfer.

It is also anticipated that a safe setting will leverage CILogon 'Groups', whereby a user's membership in a Group corresponding to a dataset/asset indicates they have been approved to access the dataset/asset, to facilitate access to the data stored in

their setting. In other words, a safe setting will be able to interface with CADRE’s CILogon/COMange API to determine a user’s group membership to allow/deny access to that user to data in that setting.

5.2 Data Entities

5.2.1 CADRE User accounts

CADRE user types will be of 3 types:

1. User – requesters, collaborators
2. Approver – approves Data Sharing Requests - request approver, data custodian/owner
3. Organisation “owner” – manages an “Organisation” and the datasets/assets associated with the Organisation (ex. ADA will be an Organisation and requestable ADA datasets will be created as belonging to that Organisation).
4. Platform Admin – administers the CADRE platform, assigns API keys to users, etc.

The CADRE user roles and associated permissions are specified in another document.

5.3 Information Security Controls

- 5.3.1 Role/permission-based access to levels of functionality in the UI and API.
- 5.3.2 Encryption in transit: https (HSTS: Http Strict Transport Security) - UI and REST API
- 5.3.3 Any documents such as deeds, etc. passed from the user to the service and that need to be secured, will be secured in the most appropriate way (encryption if necessary, etc.)
- 5.3.4 Any documents uploaded by users through the CADRE platform, the types of documents that will be allowed to upload will be constrained to a subset of types.

6 CADRE Platform Support

6.1 Model for Support

Tier	Details	Support
T0	Online Documentation, FAQ	CADRE Team
T1	Application Assistance	CADRE Team
T2	VM/Server support (Infrastructure)	CADRE Team/NCI
T3	External services	Service support; CADRE Team

7 Compliance

7.1 Policy and Legislation Compliance

A set of policy documents under which CADRE will operate is in development (12/2024). The policy documents are based on the AARC framework (<https://aarc-community.org/policy/>). The final versions of these documents will be made public and a link provided on the production CADRE platform.

8 Additional Information

8.1 Risks

- Ability to recruit development team members
- Ability to recruit experienced testers, writing test cases and then performing actual testing
- Skillset of developers in alignment with expectations
- Assumptions made in how the CADRE platform will be able to connect to external services may be incorrect.
- Assumptions about how CILogon/Comanage can be used may be incorrect.
- Long-term funding for CILogon is unknown. If use of CILogon is discontinued in the future, CADRE auth/auth and group management may need to be refactored.

9 Development Process

The development team will use a modified agile development methodology, working on 2 week sprints. The PI of the CADRE project will act as the Product Owner to drive prioritisation of the user stories/use cases in sprints. The Technical Manager and/or one of the development team members will manage the project Kanban board.

Requirements gathering is ongoing, with user stories and user scenarios being identified, verified and curated.

The development team will code according to pre-established code guidelines and error handling guidelines to ensure a consistent product across the components.

CircleCI was implemented as the CI/CD pipeline for the dev, test and staging and production instances.

9.1 Output

All source code and containers will be available through the project's Git repository.

9.2 Acknowledgments

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